

Semiconducting Carbon Nanotubes in Photovoltaic Blends: the case of PTB7:PC₆₀BM:(6,5) SWNT

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Abstract

Blends of carbon nanotubes with conjugated polymer and fullerene derivatives are complex nanocomposite systems, which have recently attracted a great research interest for their photovoltaic ability. Therefore, gaining a better understanding of the excitonic dynamics in such materials can be important to boost the efficiency of excitonic solar cells. Here, we studied the photophysics of a ternary system in which the polymer PTB7 and the fullerene derivative PCBM are integrated with (6,5) SWNTs. We highlight the contribution of SWNTs in the exciton dissociation and in the charge transfer process. These findings can be useful for the exploitation of these multi-component systems for organic photovoltaic and, in general, optoelectronic applications.

Keywords: carbon nanotubes, excitons, charge-transfer, ultrafast spectroscopy, organic photovoltaic

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1 Introduction

The concept of excitons in semiconducting carbon nanotubes was firstly introduced by T. Ando in a pioneering theoretical work published in 1997.¹ The idea of optical resonances due to excitons in carbon nanotubes was then reprised in 2004 in an experimental work by the Vardeny and Baughman groups,² and a theoretical work by the Louie group.³ In May 2005 the group of Tony Heinz,⁴ and in December 2005 the group of Christoph Lienau,⁵ found the smoking gun evidence to state that “the optical resonances in carbon nanotubes arise from excitons”, with an exciton binding energy of 420 meV for (7,5), (6,5) and (8,3) single walled carbon nanotubes (SWNTs).⁴ Finally, in 2008 the exciton size and mobility for semiconducting carbon nanotubes with (6,5) chirality were measured.⁶ Such huge research effort in understanding the fundamental photoexcitation phenomena in carbon nanotubes demonstrates that the exciton picture of carbon nanotubes is in-fact a complex scenario, involving a series of bright and dark excitons as well as higher energetic excitons lying above the bottom of the conduction band.^{7,8} Such higher excitons, in particular, can serve as probes for photogenerated charge carriers in the highly enriched (6,5) SWNT (see figure 1a).⁹⁻¹¹

The employment of SWNTs as active materials in organic photovoltaic diodes (OPVs) is very promising because of their optical absorption in the near infrared region and the relatively high carrier mobility.¹²⁻¹⁵ Given the excitonic character of OPVs it is necessary a proper electron donor/acceptor interface to achieve effective excitons splitting and charge generation. Therefore, in organic solar cells SWNTs are usually blended with appropriate electron donor/acceptor systems either in bilayer or bulk heterojunction configurations, i.e. with conjugated polymers and fullerene derivatives. However, the relatively high level of complexity of these blends and the strong dependency of their nanomorphology on the intrinsic structural properties of the constituent

materials (i.e. crystallinity)¹⁶⁻¹⁸ and on a number of process parameters (i.e. deposition techniques and casting solvent),¹⁹⁻²¹ hinder a complete and reliable characterization of these functional nanocomposites. In this scenario, photophysical studies²² can give a strong support to describe these systems, with the view to improve their photogeneration ability.

Polythieno[3,4-b]-thiophene-co-benzodithiophene (PTB7) is a promising electron-donor polymer for organic solar cells.²³ Low band-gap (around 1.6 eV) is obtained via the stabilization of a quinoidal structure from thieno-[3,4-b]thiophene, resulting in a strong absorption around 700 nm, which is the region of the maximum photon flux of the solar spectrum. In addition, it features a rigid backbone that ensures a relatively high hole mobility and environmental stability,²⁴ whereas the presence of side chains allows a good dispersibility in organic solvents and miscibility with organic acceptors, as fullerene derivatives. As a result of these advantageous properties, a photon-to-current efficiency as high as 7.4% has been reported in OPVs incorporating PTB7.^{23,25} Furthermore, the employment of a solvent mix has been demonstrated to improve the interpenetration of polymers in the blend.^{26,27} In the case of PTB7, the mix of 1,2-Dichlorobenzene ODCB/1,8-diiodooctane (DIO) (97%-3% by volume) has proven to increase the fill factor in the I-V curve.²⁵ The photophysics in PTB7:PCBM blends has been widely studied,²⁸⁻³³ and it is characterised by an ultrafast cation state formation via intra- and intermolecular charge separation, and the formation of polaronic states that is facilitated by the charge transfer character of the repeated units. Differently from P3HT, optical charge separation occurs within very small (2-20 nm) domain sizes.²⁸

Here, we extend and nicely complement our previous studies on P3HT:SWNTs blends³⁴ with a novel investigation on SWNTs in close contact with PTB7 and PCBM. We observe evidence of a

hole transfer process between SWNTs to polymer chains, thus demonstrating that SWNTs can participate actively in the exciton dissociation process of such photovoltaic blends.

2 Experimental section

2.1 Materials

The employed glass substrates were pre-cleaned by means of sonication in acetone and isopropanol and dried out under nitrogen flow. After that a 10 minutes O₂ plasma was used to clean the substrates before the deposition of the organic layers. The substrates were then transferred into the glovebox. For the active layer preparation, PTB7 and PC60BM were dissolved in 1,2-Dichlorobenzene (ODCB) (ratio 1:0.8) with concentrations of 20 mg/mL and 16 mg/mL, respectively. The (6,5) SWNTs with 0.78 nm average diameter were purchased from Aldrich and used without further purification steps. According to the manufacturer specifications, approximately 95% of the SWCNTs are semiconducting with approximately 41% of those tubes having (6,5) chirality. For the bilayers structures, SWCNTs were dispersed as purchased in N, N-Dimethylformamide (DMF), sonicated for 1 hour and centrifuged at 1200 rpm for 30 minutes. The supernatant was then collected. For the bulk and for the bare carbon nanotube samples, the SWNTs were dispersed in ODCB and tip sonicated for 1.5 hours. The active layer was spin-coated at 1200 rpm, yielding a thickness of about 80 nm as measured by profilometry. For the structure SWNT/PTB7: PCBM, a relatively brief oxygen plasma treatment (5 seconds of exposure) was performed to the active layer before deposition of the SWNTs, with the aim to improve DMF wettability on the active layer.

2.2 Optical measurements

Steady state absorption spectra have been acquired with a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer Lambda 1050 WB. Ultrafast differential transmission measurements have been performed with a Ti:Sapphire amplified laser system (repetition rate of 1 kHz, pulse duration of about 100 fs, central wavelength at 780 nm). Excitation pulses have been obtained with second harmonic generation or by optical parametric amplification. Chirp-free transient differential transmission ($\Delta T/T$) has been collected by using an optical multichannel analyser (OMA) with a dechirping algorithm.

2.3 Density functional theory calculations

The dimers of TB4 and TB7 (two monomers of TB4 and two monomers of TB7, respectively) molecules have been sketched with the Avogadro package.³⁵ The optimization of the ground state geometry and the calculation of the electronic transitions have been performed with the package ORCA 3.0.3,³⁶ using the B3LYP functional³⁷ in the framework of the density functional theory. The Ahlrichs split valence basis set³⁸ and the all-electron nonrelativistic basis set SVPalls1 have been employed.³⁹ Moreover, the calculation utilizes the Libint library.⁴⁰ Simulations have been performed on a Dell Precision Tower Workstation 7910, mounting Dual Intel Xeon processors (10 cores, 2.35GHz) and 64 Gb of RAM memory.

3 Results and discussion

To elucidate the role of SWNTs in the exciton dynamics of PTB7:PCBM blends (see figure 1b for the chemical structure of the polymer), we employed ultrafast pump-probe spectroscopy to study the photophysics of three sample configurations, characterised by a different interfacial arrangement between the PTB7:PCBM blends and the nanotubes, namely: **1.** (6,5) SWCNT films are deposited below or **2.** on top of the bulk heterojunction layer and **3.** SWNT:PTB7:PCBM

heterojunction blend (figure 1c). The steady-state UV-VIS optical absorptions of the three configurations are shown in Figure 1d. We can clearly distinguish the polymer absorption peak centred at 650 nm with its two vibronic replica at 625 and 680 nm and the broad PTB7:PCBM absorption at 400-500 nm, while the presence of (6,5) SWNTs is testified by the peak in the infrared region at around 1 μm . We computed the optical absorption of PTB7 at the density functional theory (DFT) level (see supplementary information), to confirm that the spectral features in the visible region were indeed due to the polymer optical transitions. The relative increase of the polymer vibronic peak at 625 nm suggests that the presence of (6,5) SWNTs leads to an enhancement of the degree of order of the polymer, as it has been already observed for blends of P3HT:SWNTs in previous investigations.⁴¹⁻⁴³

Figure 1. (a) Chemical structure of PTB7. (b) Scheme of the proposed charge transfer mechanism. (c) The three different sample configurations studied for PTB7:PCBM blend with addition of (6,5) SWNTs. (d) Evolution of the steady state absorption spectra of the PTB7:PCBM samples with three different configurations upon addition of the (6,5) SWNTs.

We highlighted the contribution of SWNTs to the overall deactivation dynamics by pumping selectively either the polymer:fullerene system at 400 nm or the (6,5) SWNTs first exciton S_1 at 870 nm, and probing both in the UV-VIS (450-750 nm) and IR (900-1200 nm) spectral regions. The normalised differential transmissions (excitation at 400 nm) in the visible region for the three configurations are reported in Figure 2a for time-delay of 1 ps. In this case, in which we mostly excite and probe the polymer:fullerene system, we can observe that the signal is dominated by the ground-state bleaching (PB) of PTB7. The change in the vibronic ratio between the three samples reflects the relatively higher degree of intermixing in the BHJ configuration than the bilayer ones.

The transient photodynamics of the polymer probed at 680 nm (figure 2b) shows a faster dynamics for the bilayer structures containing SWNTs with respect to the bare PTB7:PCBM heterojunction blend, an effect that can be attributed to an enhanced excitonic relaxation in the presence of SWNTs. In these regards, it has been reported that SWNTs can act as dissociation centres and minimize the radiative recombination at a polymer/SWNT interface.⁴⁴ Instead, we attribute the slower dynamics in the ternary SWNT:PTB7:PCBM blend to the formation of SWNTs aggregates⁴⁵ that disrupt the PTB7:PCBM interpenetrated network and, thus, reduce the occurrence of charge dissociation events.

In Figure 2c we show the differential transmission pumping at 870 nm in the region of the first exciton, S_1 , of the (6,5) SWNTs. The PB peaks of PTB7:PCBM/SWNT and of pure SWNTs largely overlap, while SWNT/PTB7:PCBM and the show a slight blue-shift of the peak. Again, this effect can be explained in terms of a different interfacial architecture between the polymer:fullerene blend and the nanotubes layer and presence of nanotubes aggregates responsible for red-shifted absorption.⁴⁵ In particular, the TA spectra suggest that when we either cast the nanotubes on top of the polymer:fullerene blend (structure 2) or blend them with the polymer/fullerene (structure 3) there is more intermixing and, thus, less nanotubes aggregation than in the case of the PTB7:PCBM:SWNT configuration (structure 1). Such morphological scenario is further corroborated by the decay dynamics (figure 2d), which displays a similar decay of the SWNT signal film with the PTB7:PCBM/SWNT one (structure 2), whereas a slower decay is noticed for the PTB7:PCBM:SWNT and for the SWNT/P3HT:PCBM sample (structure 3 and 1, respectively), indicating a more effective intermixing of SWNTs with the polymer:fullerene blend for those latter configurations. We attribute the higher degree of intermixing of bilayer structure 3 than structure

2 to the swelling effect of the nanotube solution in DMF on the underlying polymer:fullerene layer, which ultimately facilitates mixing.

Figure 2. (a) Normalised differential transmission spectrum in the UV-VIS region at a pump excitation of 400 nm (pump-probe delay 1 ps). (b) Normalized kinetics of the four samples at a probe wavelength centred at 680 nm, which coincides with the main absorption of the polymer (c) Normalized transient $\Delta T/T$ spectra in the IR for a pump excitation at 870 nm (pump-probe delay 1 ps). (d) Normalized dynamics probed at 1025 nm upon selective excitation of the S_1 transition.

When exciting the S_1 of SWNTs and probing in the visible range (Figure 3a), we observe two PB signals corresponding to the S_{22} transition of the (6,5) SWNT at 580 nm and, in addition, a peak at 680 nm due to the same transition of the (7,5) chirality that is also present in the SWNTs mixture. Interestingly, we note a relatively narrower PB peak from the nanotubes in the bilayers structures,

and a slightly red-shifted signal for the (6,5) SWNTs, for the heterojunction blend when compared with the pure SWNTs sample. Such differences detected in the transient absorption spectra are also evident from the time-decay plots recorded at probe wavelengths of 590 nm, 680 nm and 690 nm (Figure 3b, c and d). In particular, if we probe at a wavelength corresponding to the S_2 transition for the (6,5) SWNTs (580 nm), all the time-decays approach to each other, for the exception of a slight fast decay in the first picosecond observed for the PTB7:PCBM/SWNT consistent with a better dispersion and a higher loading of SWNTs when compared to the bare sample. Similarly, the (7,5) SWNTs exciton also follows the same decay for all the samples (figure 3c). However, at 690 nm we note a faster deactivation dynamics for the bulk heterojunction structure PTB7:PCBM:SWNT than the other three configurations and pure SWNTs samples. This suggests a possible ultrafast (within 1 ps) charge transfer between PTB7 and SWNTs. In this scenario, the electron would be delocalized either within the nanotube domains³⁴ or, given the close proximity between PCBM (-3.7 eV) and nanotubes (-3.8 eV) LUMO levels, can be transferred to the fullerene. This scenario, however, is difficult to validated due to the large spectral overlap between the polymer and fullerene absorption spectrum.

Figure 3. (a) Differential transmission spectra for the three different structures studied and bare SWNTs excited at 870 nm and probed in the visible region (delay of 1 ps). Differential transmission dynamics for all the samples probed at (b) 580 nm, (c) 680 nm and (d) 690 nm.

Therefore, to acquire more details on the possible charge transfer mechanism between SWNTs and PTB7, we analysed the building up of the transient spectra within the first picosecond (figure 4a-d, excitation 870 nm). Starting from the pure SWNTs sample consisting of a mixture of (6,5) and (7,5) chiralities (fig. 4a), we see that PB signal at 675 nm due to the (7,5) SWNTs is more intense than the (6,5) at the early pump-probe time-delays, whereas their intensities become comparable after 400 fs. Interestingly, for the PTB7:PCBM:SWNT bulk heterojunction sample (fig. 4b), we see clear evidence of a spectral contribution at 690 nm that can be linked to the polymer PB, which decays almost within our time-resolution (150-250 fs). The observation of the

polymer PB signal while resonantly pumping the carbon nanotubes can be correlated to a hole transfer from the carbon nanotubes to the polymer. If we pass to the bilayer structures (figure 4 c,d), we cannot see evidence of hole transfer from the nanotubes to the polymer for the PTB7:PCBM/SWNT sample, while the higher intermixing achieved for the SWNT/PTB7:PCBM then the bilayer structures allow a certain degree of nanotube/polymer:fullerene interaction (fig. 4d), as indicated by the early PTB7 bleaching appearing for time-delays lower than 200 fs. We also studied the ultrafast SWNTS $\rightarrow$ PBT7 hole-transfer in blends with higher nanotubes loading, to highlight better such an effect (figure S2).

Figure 4. Transient differential transmission spectra pumping at 870 nm and probing in the visible region, for pump-probe time delays minor than 1 ps for (a) SWNTs, (b) PTB7:PCBM:SWNT, (c) PTB7:PCBM/SWNT and for (d) SWNT/PTB7:PCBM, respectively.

4 Conclusions

In conclusion, we have presented a photophysical study of the behaviour of semiconducting SWNTs placed in close contact with a polymer PTB7 and the fullerene derivative PCBM. We investigated different configurations of this film structures, with the nanotubes as a separate layer above or below PTB7:PCBM, or with the SWNTs in a ternary bulk heterojunction blends. We found evidence of ultrafast SWNTs→PTB7 hole transfer, an effect that is strongly dependent on sample configuration and nanotubes proximity to the polymer-rich regions. These measurements demonstrate an active role of the nanotube in the excitonic photodynamic of such photovoltaic blends and, hence, can be useful for the optimization of photovoltaic nanocomposites integrating SWNTs as active material.

Supporting information

See supplementary information for the DFT calculations on PTB7 dimers and the TA experiment at higher SWNTs loading.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

Acknowledgments

G.M.P is supported by the H2020 ETN SYNCHRONICS under a grant agreement 643238. This article may be downloaded for personal use only. Any other use requires prior permission of the

author and AIP Publishing. This article appeared in Journal of Applied Physics 125, 083101 (2019) and may be found at <https://aip.scitation.org/doi/abs/10.1063/1.5086504>.

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Supplementary information for

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Theoretical Calculations of Electronic States in TB4 and TB7 dimers

In Figure S1 we show the absorption spectra of a TB4 dimer (blue curve) and of a TB7 dimer (orange curve). We simulated the absorption spectra of dimers and not a long chain because of the high computational cost: the TB7 dimer corresponds to 207 atoms.

Figure S1. Simulated absorption spectra of a TB4 dimer (blue) and a TB7 dimer (orange).

TB4 dimer:

State	Wavelength (nm)	f_{osc}
1	555.1	1.381155279
2	500.3	0.152454571
3	466.5	0.072188543
4	439.3	0.457912595
5	414.5	0.012196658
6	408.9	0.002497375
7	383.5	0.276166151

TB7 dimer:

State	Wavelength (nm)	f_{osc}
1	585.9	1.005246319
2	515.4	0.605680096
3	490.1	0.015934420
4	446.0	0.463676979
5	432.8	0.003142737
6	410.2	0.001325739
7	390.7	0.259499127

TB4 dimer XYZ coordinates:

H	-54.41015864197898	-18.45380872391300	-5.41193577159912
C	-53.38597884910736	-18.05821808056002	-5.54383457425076
H	-53.47803742753101	-17.00878986739765	-5.88020898427396
H	-54.22188008229496	-17.75400118371168	-2.88524264677720
H	-52.90980571494033	-18.63120391645922	-6.35966864378765
H	-53.33724479965679	-16.31678568914518	-3.40854332165233
C	-53.20242489171277	-17.36716216688968	-3.08536886910912
H	-60.18504222968738	-24.46095611079297	-0.42650342352332
H	-58.88293641671951	-25.47003087100085	0.25888799157525
C	-52.57990002438001	-18.15761451323039	-4.24495908853423
C	-59.66529100341470	-24.73021945282176	0.51050156393515
H	-52.47687508834222	-19.22255537494513	-3.96395795075639
H	-53.32122030924597	-19.12776282206772	-0.92187921670471
C	-52.39254841804032	-17.37556641980054	-1.77886235411837
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H	-21.11111171351697	-1.37655524857555	-0.86017006222094
H	-21.56666713645637	-0.75688979963602	0.73161588714898

Transient absorption at higher loading of SWNTs

To better observe the bleaching from the polymer while selective pumping the SWNTs, we studied a PTB7:SWNT sample with a higher loading of nanotubes. For this sample a 2:0.5 mg/l polymer:SWNT ratio was employed. The polymer and the SWNT were dispersed in ODCB and stirred overnight at 60 °C. The solution was then ultrasonicated for 1 hour and ultra-centrifugated at 12000 rpm for 15 min, the supernatant was collected and drop cast in a glass substrate. The transient absorption spectra pumped at 870 nm while probed in the visible region is presented in Figure S1.

Figure S2. a) Transient differential transmission spectra and b-c) dynamics decays for a PTB7:SWNT drop casted sample pumped at 870 nm and probed in the visible region.